

A DYNAMIC CLUSTERING-BASED NEIGHBORHOOD STRUCTURE FOR MOEA/D

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Abstract

Multi-objective Evolutionary Algorithm based on Decomposition (MOEA/D) is a multi-objective optimization algorithm that utilizes a divide-and-conquer strategy. The MOEA/D algorithm breaks down a multi-objective optimization problem (MOP) into a number of sub-problems and optimizes these sub-problems concurrently. This algorithm uses a collaborative euclidean-based neighborhood structure for reproduction and information sharing in its optimization mechanism. This neighborhood structure is computed once and maintained throughout the algorithm execution. In this extended abstract, a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition with dynamic clustering (MOEA/D-CL) is proposed. The MOEA/D-CL employs a flexible neighborhood structure which is generated using a clustering technique. This algorithm is proposed with the intention to encourage searching for more diversified solutions when solving complex MOPs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Multi-objective optimization (MOO) plays an important role in solving many real-world optimization problems. These problems require an optimization of more than one objective such as DNA sequence design [1], traffic engineering [2], and wireless network routing [3] and they are known

as multi-objective problems (MOPs). The objectives of MOPs are often contracting with one another. An MOP can be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize } F(x) &= (f_1(x), \dots, f_m(x))^T \\ \text{s.t. } x &\in \Omega \end{aligned}$$

where $m \geq 2$ is the number of objectives and the set Ω is the feasible set of decision vectors [4].

In MOO, the focus is to generate a set of non-dominated solutions instead of generating a single solution that is able to optimize all the objectives being considered. These non-dominated solutions forms a Pareto front and they are known as Pareto-optimal solutions. Let's consider an example of comparing two solutions, namely Sol_A and Sol_B . If Sol_A is better than Sol_B , in terms of all objectives, then Sol_A is said dominating Sol_B .

In recent years, multi-objective evolutionary algorithms (MOEAs) are commonly used to solve MOPs. Many variants have been proposed such as U-NSGA-III [5], HypE [6], SMS-MOEA [7], and MOEA/D [8, 9]. Among these variants, the decomposition concept of MOEA/D has been widely studied due to its efficiency and simplicity in solving MOPs. Thus, this invokes our interest to investigate and improve upon MOEA/D.

MOEA/D is a population-based algorithm that utilizes a number of individuals in its optimization mechanism. MOEA/D divides an MOP into several sub-problems using an aggregation technique. These sub-problems are defined based on evenly-spaced weight vectors. In other words, each sub-problem has a distinct weight vector set, λ . Each

sub-problem is then assigned to each individual in the population. With the concept of nearby sub-problems share similar solutions, MOEA/D defines a static euclidean-based neighborhood structure based on the sub-problems [8]. The neighborhood is then utilized to reproduce new individuals and broadcasting better solution to other individuals within the neighborhood. As the neighborhood structure is determined once and maintained throughout the algorithm execution, similar individual will mate and share information repeatedly. Due to this exploitation process among the nearby individuals, the newly produced solutions are expected to be similar (i.e. the diversity of newly produced solutions is low). In order to improve the diversity of the solutions which are tied to each individual in a population, a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition with dynamic clustering (MOEA/D-CL) is proposed. The proposed neighbourhood structure replaces the static euclidean-based neighbourhood structure, and it is aimed to encourage exploration in the optimization process when solving complex MOPs (e.g. non-convex and disconnected MOPs). In the next section, the working mechanism of MOEA/D and some initial idea of MOEA/D-CL will be described.

2 Some Initial Ideas

MOEA/D relies on a decomposition technique to divide a MOP into sub-problems. Three decomposition techniques have been integrated by MOEA/D (i.e. weighted sum approach, Tchebycheff approach and Boundary Intersection (BI) approach) [8]. In weighted sum approach, a list of evenly distributed weight vectors set is firstly generated. Each individual in the population is then associated with a set of weight vectors. The associated weight vectors is used to define a fitness function, which is also known as the sub-problem. The fitness function for an individual k can be formulated as:

$$\text{maximize } \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^k f_i$$

where $\lambda_i^k \geq 0$ for all $i = 1, \dots, m$ and $\sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i^k = 1$

To understand the structure of an individual, let's consider a two-objective MOP (f_1 and f_2) that has two variable (x and y). As shown in Figure 1, each individual has a fitness function and will attempt to find a better solution (i.e. the variables) that has higher fitness value throughout an algorithm execution cycle. In order to compute the fitness function, each individual keeps a set of weight vectors and a list of variables. For example, let's consider an individual, *individual^k*, who keeps two variables of $x = 12$ and $y = 5$ and weight vectors set of $\lambda_1^k = 0.9$ and $\lambda_2^k = 0.1$. The fitness for this individual can be calculated as follows: $(0.9)(f_1) + (0.1)(f_2) = (0.9)(500) + (0.1)(25) = 452.5$.

Figure 1: Example of the Structure of an Individual k with Two-objective in MOEA/D

In the MOEA/D proposed by Zhang and Li, it is assumed that nearby individuals share similar solutions [8]. Thus, they proposed a static neighborhood structure based on euclidean distance ($Dist_{EUC} = \sqrt{(\lambda_i^k - \lambda_i^{k+1})^2 + (\lambda_{i+1}^k - \lambda_{i+1}^{k+1})^2}$) between the weight vectors of two individuals. The euclidean-based neighborhood is formed on the normalized objective spaces (refer to Figure 2), which is the domain of sub-problems (i.e. weighted sum with different weight vector coefficients).

Figure 2: Euclidean-based Neighborhood Structure of Two-Objective MOP on Normalized Objective Space

The euclidean-based neighborhood is determined once during initialization. This neighborhood structure is then maintained throughout an algorithm execution cycle. The neighborhood is then used in reproduction and information sharing process. This static structure of neighborhood will eventually lead to loss of diversity in the new solution and it tends to stuck at local optimum. To increase the diversity of newly produced solutions, the MOEA/D-CL is proposed. The proposed algorithm introduces a dynamic clustering-based neighborhood structure. A clustering method is applied using different number of cluster centroids to create a dynamic neighborhood structure (refer to Figure 3).

Figure 3: A Clustering Technique Applied on the Normalized Objective Space of Two-objective MOP

The clustering method is applied on the normalized objective space. As shown in Figure 3, the cluster neighborhood size has an inverse relationship with the number of cluster centroids.

As the number of cluster centroids increases, the trend of searching will be moving from exploration to exploitation. Thus, by modifying the number of cluster centroids, the searching in the algorithm can be guided to have more exploration or exploitation. In MOEA/D-CL, we intend to utilize the change on the number of cluster centroids dynamically throughout an algorithm cycle to encourage more exploration compared to static euclidean-based neighborhood. The algorithm is expected to obtain a more diverse solutions.

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